

THE EFFECT OF PARENT'S ATTITUDES ON THE LEADERSHIP BEHAVIORS OF STUDENTS AT THE FACULTY OF SPORT SCIENCES

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to explore the effect of parental attitudes of students at the Faculty of Sports Sciences on their leadership behaviors.

For data collection, two instruments were used in the current study to explore the leadership behaviors of students and their parental attitudes. These were: 'The Leadership Behavior Scale' which was developed by Hemphill and Coons [8] and adapted into Turkish by Önal [10] and 'The Parental Attitude Scale' which was developed by Kuzgun and Eldeklioglu [9]. These questionnaires were administered to a total of 590 students consisting of 376 male and 214 female students. For data analysis, the SPSS statistical packet program was used for frequency analysis, and independent t-tests, one-way ANOVA and Tukey test were run to find out the source of the difference among different groups of participants. In addition, correlation analysis was performed to reveal the relationship between the students' leadership behaviors and parental attitudes.

The findings of the study showed that there was a statistically significant positive correlation between parental attitudes and leadership behaviors of the participants.

Based on this finding, it was revealed that the more the parental attitudes of the participants increased, the more the students' leadership behaviors increased.

Key words: Parental Attitude, Leadership Behavior, Sports, Physical Education.

Introduction

Attitude is a kind of behavior which is formed in response to a particular situation faced by an individual and which has its origins in psychology and is related to the personality of the individual [11]. The importance of family education in the development of the individual and its impact on attitude are recognised by all scientists and explained from different perspectives. Cüceloglu [5] explains the behavioral characteristics of individuals and states that the family and the environment in which they grow need to be taken into consideration, because there is a direct relationship between the behavior of the individual and the attitude of his/her family. Parental attitudes are based on parental control and the socialization of the child. The basic point here is what kind of socialization and control the parents provide their children. Parents' first and main role is to teach, influence

and control [3]. In this respect, three different parental attitudes including the democratic, protective and authoritarian were investigated within the scope of this research.

Democratic parents possess the kind of attitude which means that they love their children, they really care about them and they have a good relationship with them, which is based on love and respect. They try to solve problems by consulting with their children. Moreover, there is a sincere and friendly atmosphere rather than tension in the family [16].

An overprotective attitude is based on excessive control, and the parents who have this attitude show great interest in and affection towards their child. All of the child's desires are fulfilled. Children who grow up in such extremely protective families can be dependent and they have a lack of self-confidence and emotional problems [15].

Parents with oppressive-authoritarian parental attitudes do not consider their child's

developmental stages, personality traits and desires and they expect the child to behave in the way they want them to, while punishing the child who does not comply with their own desires [11]. These penalties may include shouting, censure, scolding or even physical violence.

Many studies have been conducted and a number of theories developed about leadership in relevant literature. There are many taxonomies regarding the concept of 'leadership' in literature. Based on the most common classifications, 'Feature Theories' advocates that leadership skills depend on inherent characteristics and 'Behavioral theories' approaches this issue by evaluating leadership through effective leader behavior. 'Contingency Theories' consider the effective leaderships with a focus on the conditions which the individuals experience. 'Current Approaches' assess the leader through vision ownership, creativity and the skill of vision for the future. Previously, the definition of leadership was related to politics, the military and religion. With advancements in the industrial revolution, the studies in the field of leadership increased as the needs of these organizations differed as well as the increase in the importance of the organization [1].

In our research, there are two dimensions of leadership. The first are leaders who prefer the dimension of construction. They are more focused on business and professionalism; they expect their subordinates to reach certain standards of success and give importance to the completion of work at the right time. The second are leaders who prefer the dimension of tolerance; they are more people-oriented, behave in a friendly way to subordinates, are open to communication, and support their subordinates [14].

Due to the age of science and technology, we are facing a dynamic and ever-changing and developing environment. We are experiencing a period of rapid depletion in social relations and human relations. Considering that there is socialism on the basis of the concept of sports, it has become important to investigate how effective the family education is on leadership behaviors and how much bilateral communication dominates.

The aim of this study is to explore the effect of parental attitudes of the students at the Faculty of Sports Sciences on their leadership behaviors.

Material and methods

For data collection, two instruments were used in the current study to explore the students' leadership behaviors and their parental attitudes. These were: 'The Leadership Behavior Scale' which was developed by Hemphill and Coons [8] and adapted into Turkish by Önal [10] and 'The Parental Attitude Scale' which was developed by Kuzgun and Eldeklioglu [9]. These questionnaires were administered to a total of 590 students consisting of 376 male and 214 female students.

For data analysis, the SPSS statistical packet program was used for frequency analysis, and independent t-tests, one-way ANOVA and the Tukey test were run to find out the source of the difference among different groups of participants. In addition, correlation analysis was performed to reveal the relationship between the students' leadership behaviors and parental attitudes.

SPSS 16 statistical packet programme was used to evaluate the acquired data and meaningfulness level is accepted as ($p < 0,05$).

Results

An insight into the gender of the participants in Table 1 showed that 63.8 % of the participants are men whereas 36.2 % of them are women. In terms of age, it was revealed that 29.7 % of the participants are between the ages 21 and below while 48.4 % of them are between 21-25 ages and 21.9 % of them are at the age of 26 and above.

As for the distribution of participants in terms of departments as indicated in Table 1, it was revealed that 25.9 % of the participants are at the Department of Coaching, 23.1 of them are at the Department of Physical Education Training, 26.4 % of them are at the Department of Sports Management and 24.6 % of them are at the Department of Recreation. Considering their grades, 27.8 % of the participants are at 1st Grade, 24.6 % of them are at 2nd Grade, 25.1 % of them are at 3rd Grade and 22.5 % of them are at 4th Grade.

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Table 1. Participants' Information in terms of Demographic Features

Gender	N	%
Men	376	63.8
Women	214	36.2
Age	N	%
Age 20 and below	175	29.7
Between 21-25 ages	286	48.4
Age 26 and above	129	21.9
Department	N	%
Coaching	153	25.9
Physical Education Training	136	23.1
Sports Management	156	26.4
Recreation	145	24.6
Grade	N	%
1 st Grade	164	27.8
2 nd Grade	145	24.6
3 rd Grade	148	25.1
4 th Grade	133	22.5
Total	590	100

Table 2. The Comparison of the Participants' Parental Attitudes based on Gender

Sub-Dimension	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	t	P(sig.)
Democratic parental attitude	Men	376	3.47	,321	2,741	,006*
	Women	214	3.30	,269		
Protective parental attitude	Men	376	2.86	,274	2.165	,032*
	Women	214	3.02	,369		
Authoritarian parental attitude	Men	376	2.68	,521	2.804	,005*
	Women	214	2.97	,601		

*: p<0,05

As indicated in Table 2, it was found out that there were statistically significant differences between men and women based on their gender regarding their parental attitudes ($p<,05$). According to the findings obtained from data analysis, considering democratic

parental sub-dimension, men ($=3,47\pm,321$) had higher means compared to women ($=3,30\pm,269$). As for the protective parental attitude sub-dimension, women ($=3,02\pm,369$) had higher means than men ($=2,86\pm,274$). Regarding the authoritarian parental attitude sub-dimension, women participants ($=2,97\pm,601$) had higher means compared to men ($=2,68\pm,521$).

Table 3. The Comparison of the Participants' Leadership Behaviors based on their Gender

Sub-Dimension	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	t	P(sig.)
Initiation of Structure	Men	376	56,40	,724		
	Women	214	54,98	458		
Consideration	Men	376	55,54	,654	2,387	,004*
	Women	214	57,72	,628		

*: $p<,05$

As it is obvious in Table 3 above, it was revealed that there were statistically significant differences between men and women in terms of initiation of structure ($p=,015$) and consideration ($p=,004$) sub-dimensions. Specifically, considering the initiation of

structure sub-dimension, male students ($=56,40\pm,724$) had higher means compared to female students ($=54,98\pm,458$) and regarding the consideration sub-dimension, female students ($=57,72\pm,628$) had higher means compared to male students ($=55,54\pm,654$).

Table.4 The Comparison of the Participants' Parental Attitudes based on Age

Scale	Age	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	F	P(sig.)
Democratic Parental attitude	20 and below	175	3,04	,485		
	between 21-25	286	3,02	,551		
	between 26-30	129	3,05	,689		
Protective Parental Attitude	20 and below	175	3,08	,248		
	between 21-25	286	3,07	,458		
	between 26-30	129	3,04	,472		
Authoritarian Parental Attitude	20 and below	175	3,11	,354		
	between 21-25	286	3,07	,227		
	between 26-30	129	3,08	,452		

*: $p<,05$

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As indicated in Table 4 above, the findings obtained from the data analysis demonstrated that there were not any statistically significant differences among participants from different age groups in terms of their parental attitudes ($p > 0,05$).

As is obvious in Table 5, there was no statistically significant difference between participants from different age groups in terms of their means at the Initiation of Structure ($p = ,559$) Consideration ($p = ,368$) and sub-dimensions ($p > 0,05$).

Table.5 The Comparison of the Participants' Leadership Behaviors based on Age

Scale	Age	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	F	P(sig.)
Initiation of Structure	20 and below	175	55,05	,830	,284	,559
	between 21-25	286	54,91	,890		
	between 26-30	129	55,02	,835		
Consideration	20 and below	175	54,18	,975	,354	,368
	between 21-25	286	54,22	1,021		
	between 26-30	129	54,14	1,035		

* $p < 0,05$

Table.6 The Comparison of Participants' Parental Attitudes in terms of Departments

Scale	Department	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	F	P(sig.)
Democratic Parental attitude	Physical Education Training	136	3,04	,485	,175	,368
	Sports Management Coaching	156	3,02	,551		
	Recreation	153	3,05	,689		
		145	3,06	,436		
Protective Parental attitude	Physical Education Training	136	3,08	,248	,279	,247
	Sports Management Coaching	156	3,07	,458		
	Recreation	153	3,04	,472		
		145	3,01	,547		
Authoritarian Parental attitude	Physical Education Training	136	3,11	,354	,235	,196
	Sports Management Coaching	156	3,07	,227		
	Recreation	153	3,08	,452		
		145	3,05	,357		

* $p < 0,05$

As indicated in Table 6, there were no statistically significant differences among participants in terms of their parental attitudes based on their departments ($p > 0,05$).

As seen in Table 7, there were statistically significant differences across participants from different departments in terms of Initiation of Structure ($p = ,000$) and Consideration ($p = ,000$) sub-dimensions ($p < 0,05$).

In this respect, considering initiation of structure sub-dimension, Sports Management department students ($=55,73\pm,738$) were found to show more task-oriented leadership behaviors compared to the students at the Physical Education Training ($=54,23\pm,703$), Coaching ($=54,12\pm,949$) and Recreation ($=54,13\pm,891$) Departments. As for the

Consideration sub-dimension, the students at the Coaching Department ($=55,82\pm,019$) were found to have more people-oriented leadership behaviors compared to the students at the Departments of Physical Education Training ($=54,05\pm,752$), Sports Management ($=54,16\pm,971$) and Recreation ($=54,05\pm,881$).

Table 7. Comparison of the Participants' Leadership Behaviors based on their Departments

Sub-dimensions	Department	N	Means	Std. Dev.	F	P(sig.)	Difference
Initiation of structure	1- Physical Edu. Tr.	136	54,23	,703	4,245	,000*	2-1
	2- Sports Man.	156	55,73	,738			2-3
	3- Coaching	153	54,12	,949			2-4
	4- Recreation	145	54,13	,891			
Consideration	1- Physical Edu. Tr.	136	54,05	,752	4,351	,000*	3-1
	2- Sports Man.	156	54,16	,971			3-2
	3- Coaching	153	55,82	1,019			3-4
	4-Recreation	145	54,05	,881			

*p<0,05

Table 8. Comparison of Participants' Parental Attitudes Based on Grade

Scale	Grade	N	Means	Std. Dev.	F	P(sig.)
Democratic Parental Attitude	1 st Grade	164	2,98	,645	,248	,148
	2 nd Grade	145	3,02	,625		
	3 rd Grade	168	3,04	,617		
	4 th Grade	133	3,03	,687		
Protective Parental Attitude	1 st Grade	164	3,06	,578	,341	,268
	2 nd Grade	145	3,07	,568		
	3 rd Grade	168	3,11	,534		
	4 th Grade	133	3,10	,579		
Authoritarian Parental Attitude	1 st Grade	164	3,14	,487	,314	,324
	2 nd Grade	145	3,16	,436		
	3 rd Grade	168	3,09	,439		
	4 th Grade	133	3,08	,462		

*p<0,05

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As demonstrated in Table 8 above, the findings of the study based on data analysis yielded no statistically significant difference

between the participants from four different grades considering their parental attitudes ($p > 0,05$).

Table 9. The Comparison of the Participants' Leadership Behaviors Based on Grade

Sub-dimensions	Grade	N	Means	Std. Dev.	F	P(sig.)	Difference
Consideration	1 st Grade	164	55,05	,585	1,395	,000*	4-1
	2 nd Grade	145	55,11	,563			4-2
	3 rd Grade	168	56,54	,635			3-2
	4 th Grade	133	56,65	,615			3-1
Initiation of structure	1 st Grade	164	56,35	,254	1,268	,328	---
	2 nd Grade	145	56,38	,107			
	3 rd Grade	168	56,44	,276			
	4 th Grade	133	57,41	,341			

* $p < 0,05$

The findings of the study showed that although there was not a statistically significant difference in terms of initiation of the structure ($p = ,482$) sub-dimension, there was a statistically significant difference between different grades in terms of consideration ($p = ,000$) sub-scale ($p < 0,05$).

Based on this finding, regarding consideration sub-dimension, the 4th grade ($=56,65 \pm ,615$) and the 3rd grade students ($=56,54 \pm ,635$) were found to show more people-oriented leadership behaviors compared to the 1st grade ($=55,05 \pm ,585$) and the 2nd grade students ($=55,11 \pm ,563$).

Table.10 Analysis of Correlation between Participants' Parental Attitudes and Leadership Behaviors

Sub-dimensions	Leadership Behaviors	
Democratic Parental Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.796**
	P	.000
	N	590
Protective Parental Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.772**
	P	.000
	N	590
Authoritarian Parental Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.734**
	P	.000
	N	590

* $p < 0,05$

The analysis of the data showed that there was a strong positive correlation between

participants' democratic, protective and authoritarian parental attitudes and their

leadership behaviors ($r=.796$, $r=.772$, $r=.734$, $p<0.01$).

Based on this finding, it is possible that the higher means the participants have in terms of their parental attitudes, the higher means they have in terms of their leadership behaviors.

Discussion and conclusions

Parents' attitudes and the leadership behaviors of students studying at the Atatürk University Faculty of Sport Sciences were investigated and the following conclusions were reached.

As a result of comparing the parental attitudes of the participants according to their gender; women students have a more protective and authoritarian attitude from their families, male students reported that their families have a more democratic attitude. This situation can be interpreted due to the fact that Turkish parents have an authoritarian attitude because they think that girls are more in need of protection than boys. Dokuyan [6] investigated the parental attitudes of 12th-grade students and all three sub-dimensions attained the same findings. These findings support our research. Yenciun [17] investigated the attitude of parents in young adults and reached the conclusion that there is no difference according to gender. This situation contradicts our findings.

Significant differences have been reached in comparing the leadership behaviors of participants according to their gender. Accordingly, women have more averages than men at the sub-dimension of consideration. This is due to women having a more emotional structure and greater belief in sharing which may lead to the adoption of a personal leadership approach. Also, in the sub-dimension of the initiation of structure men have more averages than women. This may be due to the fact that men take a more managerial structural focus, leaving their emotions aside and acting professionally. Atar and Özbeğ [2] investigated the leadership behavior of Physical education and sports school students and have identified significant differences in favor of women. Durukan [7] investigated the leadership behaviors of physical education and

sports college students in the 1st and 4th grades and has reached similar results. These findings support our research. Solmaz ve Aydın [12] investigated the leadership behaviors of physical education and sports college students and found no significant difference according to gender. Can [4] in his study reached similar results. These findings contradict our findings. Significant differences have been reached in comparison of leadership behaviors according to the department of the participants. According to this, it is seen that sports management department students have a higher average than other department students. This situation may be due to the curriculum of the management department which teaches the establishing of a professional relationship rather than an emotional bond among employees as they take courses related to management. It is seen that the students of the coaching department have more averages at the sub-dimension of consideration. One of the most important factors affecting sporting performance when it comes to professional competence is motivation. Each athlete has a distinctive personality, due to which, the trainer should establish a mutual relation with them separately. Significant differences have been reached in the sub-dimension of consideration in comparing the leadership behaviors of the participants. According to these results, it is seen that 4th grade students have more averages. This situation may be because of the increasing experience of life together with the difficulties experienced and the ability to empathise becoming more advanced in individuals. A strong positive relationship was found between the attitudes of the participants' parents and their leadership behaviors. This situation should show whether the authoritarian, protective or democratic attitude is exhibited; It can be interpreted in the way that young people who are cared for by their family, and who remain in communication with them can also develop leadership characteristics.

As a result; young people give direction to the sport of a country through the education they receive. In order to achieve their personal goals and organizational goals it is important to be individuals that have leadership spirit. Considering the fact that parental attitudes

affect the leadership behavior of individuals; awareness should be raised among families of how effective education and communication are on individuals. This consciousness can be enhanced with conditions such as personal development, empathy, communication skills courses, seminars, symposiums, conferences.

In this way, young people who are educated in the faculty of sports sciences and their families will be able to establish better communication and are more confident in terms of personalities and individuals with more advanced leadership characteristics; they will begin to contribute more to Turkish sport.

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